

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

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YANGI O'ZBEKISTON RIVOJIDA AYOLLAR DEMOKRATIK JARAYONLARNING FAOL ISHTIROKCHISI.

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Annotatsiya: Maqolada Yangi O'zbekistonda xotin-qizlar demokratik jarayonlarning kuzatuvchisi emas, balki faol ishtirokchisi ekanligi, gender teglik masalasi, xotin-qizlarga davlat tominidan yaratilayotgan keng ko'lamli imkoniyatlar haqida fikr yuritilgan. Jahondagi ilg'or mamlakatlarda shakllangan demokratiya tamoyillari avvalo, ayol huquqi, inson muammosi esa, ko'p jihatdan ayol muammosi ekanligini e'tirof etilganligi hisobga olinib mamlakatimizdagi yangi islohotlarning natijadorligi haqida fikr yuritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Yangi O'zbekiston, gender teglik, "oila", "Oila ayollar", "gender munosabatlari", "Ayollar masalasi".

В РАЗВИТИИ НОВОГО УЗБЕКИСТАНА ЖЕНЩИНЫ ЯВЛЯЮТСЯ АКТИВНЫМИ УЧАСТНИКАМИ ДЕМОКРАТИЧЕСКИХ ПРОЦЕССОВ.

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Аннотация: В статье рассматривается тот факт, что женщины в Новом Узбекистане являются не наблюдателями демократических процессов, а активными участниками, вопрос гендерной идентичности, широкий спектр возможностей, создаваемых для женщин государством. Учитывая тот факт, что принципы демократии, сформировавшиеся в передовых странах мира, прежде всего, права женщин, а проблемы человека признаются во многом женскими проблемами, обсуждались результаты новых реформ в нашей стране.

Ключевые слова: Новый Узбекистан, гендерный тег, «семья», «Семейные женщины», «гендерные отношения», «Женский вопрос».

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**IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF NEW UZBEKISTAN, WOMEN ARE ACTIVE
PARTICIPANTS IN DEMOCRATIC PROCESSES.**

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Abstract: The article discusses the fact that women in New Uzbekistan are not observers of democratic processes, but active participants, the issue of gender identity, the wide range of opportunities created for women by the state. Taking into account the fact that the principles of democracy formed in the advanced countries of the world, first of all, women's rights, and human problems are acknowledged to be largely women's problems, the results of the new reforms in our country were discussed.

Key words: New Uzbekistan, gender tag, "family", "Family women", "gender relations", "Women's issue".

Decision of the Senate of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. SQ-297-IV of May 28, 2021 "On approval of the strategy for achieving gender equality in the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030", No. PF-60 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan of January 28, 2022 " On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026", No. PF-81 of March 1, 2022 "Improving the system of working with families and women, supporting the neighborhood and religious on measures", No. PF-87 dated March 7, 2022 "On measures to further accelerate work on systematic support for families and women", PQ dated March 7, 2019 - No. 4235 "On measures to further strengthen guarantees of women's labor rights and support entrepreneurship", No. PQ-5040 of March 26, 2021 "Educational and spiritual works" on the measures to fundamentally improve the system PQ-329 dated July 22, 2022 "Decisions on additional measures to improve the system of vocational and entrepreneurship training for women and girls" and No. 388 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 22, 2021 "On the effective implementation of vocational and entrepreneurship training programs for young people and women and measures to allocate microcredits for their entrepreneurial activities No. 919 of November 20, 2019 number "Decisions on measures to further

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improve the system of providing employment to women and developing entrepreneurship among them.

The principles of democracy formed in advanced countries of the world also recognize that human rights are primarily women's rights, and human problems are largely women's problems. That is why, in the years of independence, the issue of women rose to the level of state policy, and the necessary political and legal framework was created to increase the activity of women in the construction of the state and society. Especially in recent years, deeper and more consistent reforms are being implemented in this matter. In this regard, the activities of the State Committee for Family and Women of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Institute "Family" and the movement "Family Women" are also confirmed.

In the following years, ensuring the rights and interests of women, gender equality, protecting the family, motherhood and childhood, developing entrepreneurship among women, creating new jobs for them, improving working and living conditions is the priority of the state policy. became a complaint.

It should be like that, of course. After all, as stated in the President's work "New Development Strategy of Uzbekistan", today half of the working population in our republic is made up of women. The share of women in the management system of our country has reached 33%. About one and a half thousand women are working in various leadership positions across our country. 32% of the deputies of the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis, 23% of the deputies of the Senate and the local council are women. For the first time in the history of Uzbekistan, the number of women in the national parliament has reached the level set by the UN recommendations. The parliament of our country has risen to the 37th place among 190 national parliaments in the world in terms of the number of female deputies. It is our pride that among our women there are hundreds of doctors of science, professors and academicians, who have received the titles of "People's Teacher", "People's Poet", "People's Artist". It is no exaggeration to say that our women, who have such modern knowledge and talent, and are selfless for our country, are the golden fund of our nation.

In our country, many regulatory and legal documents aimed at increasing the socio-political and social activity of women, achieving gender equality, further increasing their abilities and opportunities in various fields and industries, as well as strengthening the institution of the family have been adopted. The Women's

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Committee and its regional departments, which were previously limited in their capabilities and activity, were established on a completely new basis. Currently, more than 10,000 sisters with great knowledge and life experience are serving in this system. The Republican Center for Rehabilitation and Adaptation of Women is working. Strengthening the institution of the family later rose to the level of state policy in our country. "Oila" scientific and practical research center was reorganized and included in the government structure. The concept of strengthening the family institution was adopted.

In order to raise the scientific and cultural level of women, to provide them with decent jobs, special admission quotas for girls in higher educational institutions were introduced from 2020. This is the first experience in our history. Currently, the number of grants for girls from needy families for admission to higher educational institutions has been doubled, and special scholarships are being introduced for girls who are studying with excellent grades and need social protection. Currently, women make up about half of the workers and employees working in various fields and industries in our country. The idea that "... men and women have equal rights" established in our constitution is consistently implemented in life. "For the first time in the history of Uzbekistan, the number of women in the national parliament has reached a level consistent with the recommendations set by the United Nations. The parliament of our country has risen to the 37th place among 190 national parliaments in the world in terms of the number of female deputies. whereas, 5 years ago, we were in 128th place in this regard."

The history of philosophical teachings confirms that the theme of appreciation has been one of the constant problems of human thinking. In this regard, although the concept of "gender", which was formed in this direction and is widely used today, was introduced into scientific circulation in the second half of the 20th century, its content is ancient. This idea is confirmed by the fact that the relationship between two sexes, that is, man and woman, is expressed in the philosophy of antiquity, the philosophy of the Middle Ages, the philosophy of the Renaissance, and the philosophy of the new era.

So, "gender relations" is not a discovery of today's science, but has been researched as a subject of scientific research since ancient times. Independence made the women of Uzbekistan literally equal members of society, including political subjects. Thanks to independence, women had the opportunity to directly or

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indirectly participate in the management of the state and society. This is a historical achievement of the people of Uzbekistan, including our women. Of course, this achievement did not happen by itself. In the legislation and practice of independent Uzbekistan, the ruling worldview that "politics is men's work" has been abolished. "Women have the right to vote in all elections on equal terms with men, without any discrimination" expressed in the "Convention on the Political Rights of Women" adopted by the UN on December 20, 1952 (Article 1); "Women can be elected to all institutions established by national law, which require public elections, on equal terms with men, without any discrimination" (Article 2); All requirements of "Women have the right to occupy positions in the public-state service on the basis of equal conditions with men and to perform all public-state duties defined by the national law" (Article 3) are consistently implemented. As President Sh. Mirziyoyev noted, "It is not only the official duty of leaders at all levels, but also, first of all, the human duty to create decent work and living conditions for our loving mothers and sisters, who are angels of grace in our lives."

At the current stage of development of modernized Uzbekistan, the main factor of the reforms implemented in all spheres is man and his interests. There is no doubt that the state creates the same conditions and opportunities for people to find their value and place in the civil society that is being established in our country, which serves as a basis for practical principles in this regard.

It is no secret that women are making their due contribution to the development of New Uzbekistan and the development of civil society. In the words of the President, "... now every woman is not an observer of democratic processes, but an active and proactive participant. Important steps have been taken in recent years in our country to ensure women's rights and freedoms, dignity and gender equality. "On guarantees of equal rights and opportunities for women and men, "Adoption of laws on protection of women from oppression and violence, of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 8, 2022" Decision No. 437 on measures to organize the activities of the intelligent women's movement, No. 48 of the State Committee for Family and Women of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 11, 2022 "Measures to organize the activities of the intelligent women's movement to The command about is a clear example of this. In order to ensure equal rights and opportunities for women and men in the social, economic and political spheres, the strategy of achieving gender equality in the Republic of

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Uzbekistan until 2030 was approved. The fact that the strategy goals in this direction are clearly defined in our updated Constitution allows to form a respectful attitude towards human values and, in particular, women's rights in the country, and further increase the prestige of Uzbekistan in the international arena.

The strategy of achieving gender equality in the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030. The norms of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan on guarantees of equal rights and opportunities for women and men were developed in accordance with the long-term goals of the country defined in the development strategy of New Uzbekistan. . This document envisages a comprehensive approach to the implementation of the principle of equality between women and men in all spheres and levels of decision-making and implementation. It covers issues such as ensuring equal and quality education for all, girls in rural areas getting higher education, achieving gender equality, preventing violence, and preventing human trafficking. received. The important point is that the directions in this field are defined in accordance with the sustainable development goals of the UN until 2030. It follows from this that it is to ensure equality in economic, political and social life in order to create conditions for the realization of equal rights and opportunities of men and women and to observe fundamental human rights.

Today, the strategy of achieving gender equality is being implemented in our country. A Republican commission on issues of ensuring gender equality was established and a separate committee was established in the Senate of the Oliy Majlis. The strategy for achieving gender equality, all directions in this strategy are fully compatible with the Sustainable Development Goals of the UN until 2030. In particular, this strategy covers 9 goals:

- creation of equal opportunities and rights in the participation of men and women in social and political life;
- ensuring gender equality in protecting the rights of women and men in the economy, employment and labor migrants;
- ensuring fair and quality education for all throughout life;
- ensuring gender equality for all women, protection from violence, putting an end to human trafficking; - ensuring social protection and healthy lifestyle for all men and women;
- development of national gender statistics;
- taking into account the gender issue in planning and budgeting;

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- Ensuring wide coverage of gender issues in mass media;
- involving women in the issues of ensuring a safe ecological environment for all.

Along with social, economic and political factors, the reforms implemented in the spiritual and educational spheres are of great importance in the development strategy of the new Uzbekistan.

Building a new Uzbekistan is based on two strong pillars: a strong economy based on market principles and a strong spirituality embodying the rich heritage of our ancestors and national and universal ideals. For this purpose, it is necessary to implement the concept of "New Uzbekistan - an enlightened society".

Also, in the holy religion of Islam, a woman is honored as a dignified species. The history of the formation of the Uzbek family of the Uzbek woman is intertwined with the ancient history of our nation. Among Eastern women, the influence of Islamic beliefs is incomparable on the formation of the Uzbek woman's appearance, character, and spiritual world. In the past, respect for the man who was the head of the family, shame, and shame were considered important qualities of an Uzbek woman. In the families where such women lived, the situation of harmony and harmony was established, and the children grew up to be wonderful people. Valuable opinions are given in many sources, especially in hadiths. Examples from hadiths:

1. The most blessed of wives is the one whose burdens are easier for their husbands.

2. If husband and wife look at each other with the eyes of love and friendship, Allah will look at them with the eyes of mercy. If a husband holds his wife's hand, his sins will be poured out between his fingers.

3. Marriage is done for a woman's religion or wealth or beauty. Choose the pious one and be blessed. 4. No father can give his child more than good education and manners. Also, it is appropriate to give examples of female qualities in Uzbek folk proverbs.

Examples of proverbs:

1. A woman's hair is an angel of livelihood.

2. A house with a house is a house with grace.

3. A life with a wife is a flower, a life without a wife is a desert.

Today, the following conditions should be present for the formation of mature moral culture of women:

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1. Peaceful and good relations between family members.
2. The family should have a healthy outlook.
3. The responsibility of adults in the family in raising children.
4. The presence of a sense of gratitude for the achievements of our country, the creative works carried out in it.
5. The presence of a positive attitude in our national values, customs and traditions. It should be noted that it is a family that hears, realizes and understands about the progressive trends related to women in developed countries.

The place of a woman, a mother in the Uzbek family is of special cementing importance. Because "Love for mother is the root of love for country", "Mother's heart is in the child, child's heart is in the field", "If your mother is a stepmother, your father is not yours", "A child is clay, mother is a potter", "A child also says mother, a mother also says mother", "You know the goodness of your mother if you are a patient", etc. The consistent parenting skills of parents make them proud to be parents of good children. "If the behavior of girls is good or bad, the cause is father and mother" (Y.K. Hajib). Positive and negative situations in life, sad events, the decline of affection between people, mental and emotional stress in interpersonal relationships, the increase in the number of unhappy families, the increase in crime among young people there is no doubt that the effect on the mental environment in the family is directly related to interpersonal relations between family members and complex problems in the family.

It consists in the recognition of the impossibility of achieving a virtuous society without properly solving these problems. Qualities such as harmony, kindness, mutual respect, sweetness, mutual support in the interaction between the family members of a woman are one of the methods that increase the effectiveness in raising the young generation in a purposeful way, and imitating is a good example.

Therefore, women as role models should have such qualities, including:

- hard worker;
- order is disciplined;
- affectionate;
- patient;
- let literate children be born.

Every woman with such qualities will have a strong influence in the field of raising virtuous and respectable children. The most important factor that ensures the

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reputation of women is their exemplary human relations in everyday life, high success in work, as well as the criteria that determine their characteristics related to the scope of knowledge, worldview and ethics. In families with an exemplary attitude, children learn sincerity and patience, respect and reverence, as in oriental upbringing.

In conclusion, it should be noted that "Women's issue" has been studied to one degree or another since ancient times.

A woman has always attracted the attention of people of science and creativity with her anthropological and psychophysiological characteristics. This issue is attracting the attention of researchers and specialists even today. But this situation does not lead to the opinion that scientific research of this problem is not necessary at the present time, every era, especially the modernizing and globalizing world, requires a new approach to old problems and finding new solutions.

Implementation of urgent tasks in this direction increases the efficiency of state policy, ensures equal rights for women and men in the financial, economic and social spheres. This, in turn, has a positive effect on the standard of living of citizens.

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